

The Causal Relationship between Gross National Happiness and Economic Growth in Pakistan

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ABSTRACT: The current study aims to investigate a causal relationship between economic growth and gross national happiness in Pakistan. However, health and education spending are included in the model since they reflect the community's preferences for addressing their fundamental needs. This study employs the Vector Error Correction Model (VECM) method to examine the long-term relationships between gross national happiness (GNH), real GDP (RGDP), health expenditure (HEX), and educational expenditure (EEX) in Pakistan. Using quarterly data from 2003 to 2022, the research reveals a long-term equilibrium between the variables, which is confirmed by the co-integrating equation. The coefficients in the equation illustrate the complex relationships that exist between GNH and its determinants. Over time, there is a correlation between an increase in RGDP and a rise in GNH; however, spending on healthcare has a negative influence on GNH while spending on education has a positive impact. These findings highlight the difficulty in determining GNH and suggest that understanding social well-being requires a comprehensive approach that considers factors about health, education, and the economy. A positive RGDP in the fourth quarter and a negative one in the fifth have a major short-term impact on GNH. Health spending is not found to be significant in any quarter, while education spending has a negative significant influence in the fourth. The error correction term is significant and shows that the adjustment speed, in the long run, is about 0.131 percent. Future studies must investigate how to prioritize health and education over charitable and social support initiatives and incorporate these components into GNH evaluation structures. This study provides pertinent information on the elements influencing GNH in Pakistan and has implications for future research endeavors targeted at improving social happiness and prosperity. The research findings enhance the body of current literature by increasing knowledge of the socioeconomic determinants impacting well-being outcomes, which in turn contributes to the greater discussion on sustainable development and societal advancement.

Keywords: Gross national happiness, Real GDP, Education expenditure, Health expenditure, Vector Error Correction Model, Long-run relationship.

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1. Introduction

Economic growth is essential to preserving a country's financial stability and improving its citizens' well-being, both of which are necessary for a thriving economy. One of the most well-known and regularly used metrics for evaluating economic growth is the gross domestic product (GDP), which measures a nation's overall economic output. The gross domestic product is a measure used to evaluate a nation's economic performance. A country's GDP is frequently used for cross-national and international comparisons and is seen as a major measure of that nation's economic health. Gross National Happiness (GNH), first introduced in the 1970s by Jigme Singye Wangchuck, the Fourth King of Bhutan, is a modern measure of social well-being and happiness that emphasizes a holistic approach to development and goes beyond economic metrics like GDP (Locke, 2020).

The primary focus of this research is on the causal relationship between gross national happiness (GNH) and Pakistan's GDP growth, emphasizing that advancements in the economy improve the standard of life in general. Some studies indicate that while developing countries often experience high levels of satisfaction and happiness, there is a significant association between GNH and economic growth (Lee & Goh, 2023). Singh et al., (2023) have discussed current research indicating that factors related to cultural and social factors, in addition to economic ones, may have an impact on happiness. Despite challenges including scarce resources and uncertain political environments, spending on healthcare and education can raise living standards and promote economic growth. Such projects in Pakistan include the "Education for All" program and the Sehat Card scheme (Qureshi, 2023). When the government included GNH in its constitution in 2008, the world became aware of the organization's importance in Bhutan's development strategy (van Norren, 2023). Happiness was acknowledged as a significant element for decision-makers in a UN resolution enacted in 2011, which was spearheaded by Bhutan (O'Brien, 2013). Due to its diverse socio-cultural traits, unstable political environment, and socio-economic inequalities, Pakistan faces difficulties in implementing GNH and requires a customized plan based on regional considerations (Ngoo et al., 2020). While Bhutan's GNH plan is not directly transferable, it offers valuable insights into how development plans might embrace well-being. According to the author with the release of the Well-Being Budget in 2019, the New Zealand government changed its focus from economic measures to a more comprehensive plan that prioritized protecting the environment, promoting mental health, and reducing child poverty (Anders Hyaden, 2022). Similarly, (Boumahdi & Zaoujal, 2023) stresses that Canada relies on the Canadian Index of Wellbeing (CIW) to compute a variety of well-being indicators to impact policy.

In its Sustainable Development Strategy, Germany has placed a high priority on social cohesion and life satisfaction to reduce regional disparities and integrate well-being into economic policy (Mentes, 2023). The Scottish National Performance Framework integrates economic goals with well-being metrics to monitor progress in social inclusion, health, and education (Murphy, 2023).

According to Kanashiro Uehara (2024), Iceland's "Well-being Economy" plan prioritizes income equality, well-being, and environmental sustainability, with a focus on renewable energy and gender equality in particular. Costa Rica promotes social welfare and

environmental sustainability, fostering renewable energy, healthcare, and education. While (Berik, 2020) states that the UK has experimented with metrics such as the Happy Planet Index and the Well-being of Future Generations Act, Vermont, in the United States, measures economic, social, and environmental well-being using the Genuine Progress Indicator (GPI).

These examples demonstrate that economic indicators solely are becoming less and less helpful in characterizing the overall growth of a country. These nations adapt Bhutan's GNH principles to suit their objectives and conditions to create more comprehensive and sustainable methods of development by including happiness and well-being into their frameworks for policy.

Research questions

This study will answer the question, "What is the relationship between gross national happiness, health, education, and economic growth in Pakistan?"

Research objectives

The objectives of this research study are to examine the causal relationship between gross national happiness, economic growth, education, and health in Pakistan.

Problem statement

This study highlights the causal relationship between gross national happiness (GNH), economic growth, health expenditure, and education expenditure in Pakistan's current socio-economic framework. Understanding these relationships is crucial, as economic inequality and unequal access to quality healthcare and education are interrelated. Social support and generosity are less dependable indicators of a country's well-being than health and education, therefore conventional GNH metrics may neglect important health and education indices (Nwokolo et al., 2024). Because of this exclusion, it is hard to evaluate the advancement and general well-being of society. To appropriately reflect societal prosperity and advancement, GNH metrics must be recalculated with an emphasis on health and education.

2. Literature Review

According to (Fraumeni, 2022) there are many different facets and a complicated relationship between gross national happiness and gross domestic product. GDP growth is a measure of economic growth, which might contribute to a rise in material wealth, the development of new infrastructure, and the creation of jobs. Nevertheless, the effect on the well-being of the populace is contingent upon several variables, including the distribution of income, social fairness, and general quality of life. Economic growth is likely to be positively impacted by higher general levels of well-being, social cohesiveness, and general happiness. Individuals who possess happiness and ambition are more likely to be imaginative, creative, and dedicated to their profession, all of which support economic growth (Mouratidis, 2021).

According to the Human Capital Theory, which was developed by economists Theodore Schultz and Gary Becker, investments in health and education raise human capital, which in turn raises economic output and individual productivity (Goldin, 2024). In Pakistan, prioritizing healthcare and education leads to a healthier and more educated population, which not only enhances well-being (GNH) but also significantly contributes to long-term economic growth (GDP). (Diener et al., 2018) State that economic outcomes are impacted by happiness because it boost productivity, predicts future income, and influences how well people perform in the labor market. While long-term economic growth will increase employment and affect per capita income. The ability of the government to prove the value of human resources will be improved by ensuring the availability of infrastructure and health services, both of which will indirectly have a significant beneficial effect on community well-being. This will lead to tremendously productive and peaceful human development in the future (Dwyer, 2022).

A key component of the Grossman Model of Health and Economic Productivity is the connection between economic productivity and health. Since it can reduce absenteeism and increase worker productivity, improving healthcare in Pakistan can be seen as an investment in human capital (Ullah et al., 2021). GDP and GNH increase as a result of rising economic activity and improved population health.

Several important aspects that have an important effect on Pakistan's GDP and GNH are education and health. Supporting the healthcare system has the dual benefits of enhancing population health and productivity and reducing the financial burden that disease places on both individuals and the public treasury. Increased productivity and GNH, as well as lower death rates and higher quality of life, are all benefits of a more robust and skilled labor force (Santos et al., 2023). In a similar vein, Larrú (2021), asserts that education spending has a significant effect on Pakistan's socioeconomic environment. Individuals with an appropriate education and skill set can significantly impact economic activity. Interpersonal communication, critical thinking, and general life satisfaction are indicators of social well-being. It may therefore be advantageous to prioritize health and education in many ways, supporting Pakistan's consistent economic growth and increasing GNH.

There may be a significant relationship between economic growth and well-being based on the complicated relationship between gross domestic product and gross national happiness. In the interim, a robust economy can boost GDP and GNH by developing a positive feedback loop and raising living standards. "Education and Health Catalyst" emphasizes the important contributions that health and education provide to GDP and GNH (Locke, 2020).

High-quality education improves living standards and boosts economic output by fostering innovation and producing a trained labor force. Similar to this, a population in good health with access to first-rate healthcare improves personal well-being, lowers expenses, and promotes long-term economic growth (Vîrjan et al., 2023). Encouraging health and education as fundamental components of sustainable development programs can advance economic growth and long-term success while simultaneously enhancing individual happiness and well-being (Lambert et al., 2020).

3. Methodology

Data collection

This study examines gross national happiness, health, education, and economic growth using quarterly data from 2003 to 2022.

Research design

The research design is an organized method or blueprint that defines the study questions, sample plans, data collection strategies, data analysis instruments, and the general framework of the study. Researchers typically use the study design to determine the answer to the research question (Williams, 2007). The research design can be determined based on the research problem faced by an organization. The ontological approach examines the researcher's view of the existence and reality and this study is based on grounded reality. The author felt the significance of the problem that makes ontological sense and also found empirical evidence and facts about the Happiness Index, Economic growth, education, and health. Overall, the author's approach has been ontologically positive and interpretivist. Similarly, the epistemological approach also can be seen in positivism as the data can bring some insightful investigation and causal outcomes, and interpretivism in the sense that the results are subject to the nature of the economy. In this study, both deductive and inductive methods are applied. The deductive process entails formulating ideas and knowledge as the foundation for hypotheses. The study's deductive approach is apparent in its dependence on pre-existing theories, which mirrors the process of developing hypotheses based on a body of information. On the other hand, the inductive approach involves making generalizations from the particular data and findings of the research.

Analytical tool

The study was conducted with E-Views version 10. Using multiple regression analysis, the relationship between gross national happiness, real GDP growth, health expenditures, and education expenditures was examined. The underlying model of the study,

Econometric Model

$$HAP = \beta_0 + \beta_1 [RGDP]_1 + \beta_2 [HEX]_2 + \beta_3 [EEX]_3 + \varepsilon$$

Where HAP is the response variable (Happiness), are the predictor variables (inter-parameter measurements), β_0 is the intercept (constant term), β_i is the regression coefficients,

X_i ($i=1, 2, 3$) are the explanatory variables, and ε is the error term.

4. Results and Findings

Table 1 displays the descriptive statistics, which were used to calculate the statistics, such as mean, standard deviation (SD), and number of observations. The percentage of

GDP allocated to education was approximately 2.28 ± 0.29 percent. The real GDP growth was 4.44 ± 0.20 percent, the happiness index was 5.13 ± 0.49 , and the health expenditures were 2.59 ± 0.25 percent of GDP. A minimal range of -0.943 was seen in 2020, and as of 2022, the Real GDP was 5.967. Its maximum value was 8.958 years in 2005, 7.483 in 2001, and 6.096 in 2018. In Pakistan, there is a 1.42 difference between the greatest and lowest happiness scores. The mean (SD) percentage of education expenditure was 2.28 percent of GDP (0.29). The mean (SD) of health expenditure percentage of GDP was 2.59 (0.25). The mean (SD) of real GDP growth percentage was 4.44 (0.20) (Table 1).

	EEX	HAP	HEX	RGDP
Mean	2.277	5.130	2.592	4.443
Median	2.282	5.216	2.579	4.586
Maximum	2.746	5.831	2.954	8.958
Minimum	1.687	4.414	2.140	-0.943
Std. Dev.	0.286	0.493	0.256	2.209
Skewness	-0.321	-0.246	-0.207	-0.501
Kurtosis	2.498	1.654	1.702	3.858
Jarque-Bera	0.554	1.712	1.546	1.449
Probability	0.758	0.425	0.462	0.485
Sum	45.536	102.59	51.83	88.86
Sum Sq. Dev.	1.551	4.62	1.24	92.68
Observations	20	20	20	20

Trend Analysis

The relationship between gross national happiness, health and education expenditures, and real GDP growth throughout the study period is depicted in Figure 1 shows that real GDP growth grew from 2003 at a rate of 4.726 to 8.958 in 2005, but then started declining in 2005 and reached a value of 0.361 in 2009. The start climbs once again, reaching a value of 6.096 in 2018. Then, in 2020, it dropped even lower to negative (-0.943). Following 2020, it began to rise, and as of 2022, its value is 5.967. There have been notable variations in the happiness graph throughout time, with a maximum value of 5.83 seen in 2017 and minimum values of 4.41 in 2006 and 2008. The fluctuations in overall happiness levels across several years demonstrate a dynamic pattern of ups and downs, which is indicative of the various causes impacting the population's well-being. Health spending as a proportion of GDP has fluctuated throughout time, reaching a high of 2.95% in 2020 following a low of 2.14% in 2011. Since they exhibit both rising and falling patterns across time, these fluctuations emphasize the dynamic nature of health spending. This variation may be the result of shifting demands, developing health problems, or shifting financial circumstances that affect where resources are allocated over time. The GDP percentage allotted to education has also seen some significant shifts. In 2008, the highest percentage ever recorded was 2.74%, while in 2021, the lowest percentage was 1.68%. The variances reveal the unequal distribution of education expenditure; they indicate changes in priorities and budgetary constraints, and they display both positive and negative trends throughout time.

Figure 1 Trend behavior of the factors

The happiness, real GDP, and education expenditure diagrams show negative trends, highlighting ups and downs over certain periods. In contrast, the health expenditure graph shows a positive trend, showing a steady rise in expenditures on healthcare. These divergent patterns highlight the intricate interactions between social, economic, and health-related variables that affect a population's well-being.

This study utilizes time series analysis to examine at the relationship between economic growth, gross national happiness, health expenditures, and educational expenditures in Pakistan. Initially, the stationarity of the series was determined using the unit root test. A series is referred to as stationary if its mean and variance show no evidence of changing over time. The key objective of the augmented Dickey-Fuller (ADF) test, which was created by Dickey and Fuller (Dickey & Fuller, 1979, 1981), is to determine the unit root in the series. The ADF test is combined with the ordinary least squares (OLS) estimator to ascertain whether a unit root exists in the series.

The stationarity test results for each indicate that the variables in the econometric model are non-stationary. The second phase involves testing the differentiated factors and rejecting the null hypothesis of the unit root; in other words, all variables show stationary first difference results and the series are integrated of order 1. All variables are found to be I (1) using the ADF unit root test.

Table 2: Augmented Dickey fuller test

Variables	With constant	Probability	Trend	
			and intercept	Probability
At Level				
HAP	-1.9489	0.3086	-2.2700	0.4446
RGDP	-2.5615	0.1053	-2.5928	0.2848
HEX	-2.1401	0.2299	-2.2689	0.4452
EEX	-1.8758	0.3420	-2.0486	0.5658
1st difference				
ΔHAP	-7.7128	0.000	-7.6751	0.000
ΔRGDP	-8.7192	0.000	-8.6710	0.000
ΔHEX	-8.7888	0.000	-8.7310	0.000
ΔEEX	-8.7260	0.000	-8.6936	0.000

The variables' stationarity test results are shown in Table 2. The test results show the intercept types of variables' level and trend.

To determine if the variables are associated over the long term, a comprehensive investigation is required in the following step. The results of the co-integration test provide insight into any potential connections between these crucial metrics. The null hypothesis implies that there is no co-integration, whereas the alternative hypothesis claims that co-integration exists and indicates the presence of a long-lasting relationship. The findings of the Johansen co-integration test procedure can be used to determine the nature of this relationship. Carefully examining the trace statistics as well as the eigenvalue statistics yields information on the co-integration test's intensity and relevance.

Table 3: Co-integration test result

H₀: rank	Max-Eigenvalue			Trace		
	Statistic	0.05 Critical Value	P-Value	Statistic	0.05 Critical Value	P-Value
0	27.807	27.584	0.047	64.055	47.856	0.000
1	21.713	21.131	0.041	36.248	29.797	0.039
2	12.050	14.265	0.109	14.535	15.495	0.478
3	2.4853	3.8414	0.115	2.485359	3.8414	0.115

Table 3 presents the findings of the Johansen test procedure. The eigenvalue and trace statistics are shown using a lag length of 6 to determine the co-integration of the variables and a long-term relationship. The null hypothesis, $H_0: r=0$, shows the absence of co-integration among the factors; if this hypothesis is denied, move on to $H_0: r=1$ and so on. The number of co-integrating equations in the VECM system is indicated by the case where $H_0: r=x$ is allowed. There are two co-integrating equations, which indicate that there is a long-term relationship between the variables, according to the results of the maximum eigenvalue and trace test. This instance validates that VECM is appropriate for the estimation. Typically, VAR and VECM treat all variables as dependent and do not attribute

dependence to any one variable; however, in this study, there is only one dependent variable, therefore one co-integration may be chosen for analysis when using VECM.

To examine the determination of the existence of co-integration, the optimal lag number must be chosen before the co-integration test process. To examine the determination of the existence of co-integration, the optimal lag number must be chosen before the co-integration test process. Identifying the optimal lag length requirements for a VAR is a persistent problem. Table 4 displays the optimal lag length result. There are multiple selection criteria included in the table. The most effective lag length is chosen using the Akaike information criterion (AIC). The optimal lag length, as determined by AIC, is 6.

Table 3: Optimal lag length selection

Lag	AIC	HQ	SC	FPE
0	4.887619	4.938655	5.016105	0.001559
1	-6.336205	-6.081025	-5.693778	2.08e-08
2	-9.087861	-8.628537	-7.931492*	1.34e-09
3	-8.727159	-8.063692	-7.056849	1.94e-09
4	-8.471410	-7.603799	-6.287158	2.56e-09
5	-9.102813	-8.031058	-6.404619	1.41e-09
6	-9.969932*	-8.694032*	-6.757796	6.27e-10*
7	-9.661225	-8.181182	-5.935148	9.25e-10

* indicates lag order selected by the criterion, FPE: Final prediction error, AIC: Akaike information criterion

SC: Schwarz information criterion HQ: Hannan-Quinn information criterion

Furthermore, the normalized co-integrating coefficients displayed in Table 6 are provided by the co-integration test. The estimated Normalized Co-integrating Equation (NCE), based on the data, can be expressed as

$$\text{HAP} - 0.96\text{RGDP} - 0.836\text{EEX} + 0.769\text{HEX}$$

Table 6: Normalized co-integrating coefficients (standard error in parentheses)

1 Cointegrating Equation(s):		Log-likelihood	550.6572
HAP	RGDP	EEX	HEX
1.000000	-0.096219	-0.835942	0.678971
	(0.03760)	(0.27692)	(0.25408)

The NCE equation's coefficient signs are explained to be in reverse. These coefficients define the long-term effects of independent variables on dependent variables. The target variable, HAP, will increase in response to the rise in RGDP although since the RGDP sign is negative as said it is interpreted as positive. While HEX is hurting HAP due to its positive sign acting in reverse, EEX displays a negative sign, which this particular case

interprets as having a positive impact on HAP. All coefficients are statistically significant because, at the five percent significance level, the standard error for each coefficient was less than half of the coefficient, hence rejecting the null hypothesis.

Error correction coefficients provide estimates of the long-term rate of modifications. This means that if there is a disturbance that causes the dependent variable's mean to deviate, the shock will eventually reverse and a long-term adjustment will take place. The sign of error correction must be negative due to the nature of this reversal. The E-view results of the system estimation with error correction terms and the short-term effects of the components on HAP are displayed in Table 7. As defined and represented below, the co-integrating vector in this study is:

$$\beta^1_{HAP}(t-1) + \beta^2_{RGDP}(t-1) + \beta^3_{EEX}(t-1) + \beta^4_{HEX}(t-1) + \epsilon$$

For precision, it can be written as $\sum(\beta^i \psi_{(it-1)} + \epsilon)$

As the HAP is a dependent variable in the model, therefore, β^1 is by default estimated as 1 and the rest of its estimated form is:

<u>Cointegrating Eq:</u>	<u>CointEq1</u>	<u>St.Error</u>	<u>t-ratio</u>
HAP(-1)	1.000000		
RGDP(-1)	-0.096219	(0.03760)	-2.55888
EEX(-1)	-0.835942	(0.27692)	-3.01876
HEX(-1)	0.678971	(0.25408)	2.67222
C	-4.571303		

The same coefficients shown in the table can be represented in equation form under

$$HAP_{(t-1)} - 0.096RGDP_{(t-1)} - 0.835EEX_{(t-1)} + 0.678HEX_{(t-1)} - 4.571$$

This co-integrating vector shows long-run equilibrium among all factors of the model. In the short run, there may be variation and different shades of the results may be expected. By using the expression $\sum(\beta^i \psi_{(it-1)} + \epsilon)$, the VECM system can be generated for the short-run innovations as:

$$\Delta HAP = \alpha_1 + \sum(\beta^i \psi_{(it-1)} + \epsilon) + \sum_{i=1}^4 \theta_{1i} \Delta[RGDP]_{(t-i)} + \sum_{i=1}^4 \gamma_{1i} \Delta[HEX]_{(t-i)} + \sum_{i=1}^4 \vartheta_{1i} \Delta[EEX]_{(t-i)} + \epsilon$$

For simplification here only the given equation is estimated instead of explaining the entire VECM system where the dependent variable is HAP and the estimated result of VECM for said equation is given in Table 7.

<u>Error Correction:</u>	<u>D(HAP)</u>	<u>Standard error</u>	<u>t-statistics</u>
CointEq1	-0.131	0.061	-2.142
D(HAP(-1))	0.841	0.162	5.190
D(HAP(-2))	-0.023	0.177	-0.128
D(HAP(-3))	0.076	0.109	0.691
D(HAP(-4))	0.696	0.110	6.348
D(HAP(-5))	0.605	0.193	3.133
D(HAP(-6))	0.074	0.180	0.412

Error Correction:	D(HAP)	Standard error	t-statistics
D(RGDP(-1))	-0.014	0.041	-0.341
D(RGDP(-2))	-0.019	0.048	-0.399
D(RGDP(-3))	-0.009	0.033	-0.273
D(RGDP(-4))	-0.129	0.033	-3.861
D(RGDP(-5))	0.094	0.044	2.143
D(RGDP(-6))	-0.038	0.041	-0.940
D(EEX(-1))	-0.258	0.462	-0.557
D(EEX(-2))	-0.091	0.538	-0.170
D(EEX(-3))	-0.051	0.391	-0.131
D(EEX(-4))	-1.238	0.414	-2.990
D(EEX(-5))	0.709	0.524	1.353
D(EEX(-6))	-0.151	0.461	-0.328
D(HEX(-1))	-0.262	0.730	-0.358
D(HEX(-2))	0.067	0.837	0.080
D(HEX(-3))	0.151	0.716	0.211
D(HEX(-4))	-0.149	0.719	-0.208
D(HEX(-5))	0.436	0.789	0.552
D(HEX(-6))	0.265	0.682	0.389
C	-0.013	0.013	-1.028
R-squared	0.824	Log-likelihood	84.746
Adj. R-squared	0.724	Akaike AIC	-1.679
Sum sq. resid	0.364	Schwarz SC	-0.843
S.E. equation	0.091	F-statistic	8.247

In co-integration analysis, the coefficient for the co-integrating relationship represents the adjustment process towards long-term equilibrium after a shock. Following a shock, the CointEq1 Coefficient (-0.131) indicates how quickly the system is adjusting to the long-term equilibrium. The computed coefficient standard error (0.061) provides an indication of the degree of variability or uncertainty in the resultant value. In the context of the co-integration study, it acts as a measure for the precision of the estimate for the co-integrating link that the coefficient reflects. A lower standard error means that the estimate is more precise because it is less likely to differ considerably from the actual population parameter. The computed coefficient for the co-integrating relationship's statistical significance can be evaluated using the t-statistic (-2.142). The estimated coefficient is divided by the standard error to calculate it. In examining the lagged differences of the variable 'HAP' (presumably representing happiness), a detailed picture emerges of how past fluctuations in happiness levels contribute to the long-term relationship. The lags at 1 and 5 have statistically significant effects on the co-integrating relationship (based on t-values more than 1.95), and the lag at 4 also has a substantial influence, but in the other direction. There is no statistically significant difference between the other lags. Concurrently, significant patterns were found in the lag differences analysis for the variable "RGDP." The co-integrating connection is statistically significantly impacted by the lags at 4 and 5 (based on t-values greater than 1.95). The differences between the other lags are not statistically significant. The analysis of the lags related to health (HEX) and education (EEX) expenditures reveals that, for EEX, the lagged differences at lags 4 and 5 have statistically significant effects on the co-integrating relationship (t-values greater than 1.95), whereas, for HEX, none of the lagged differences show statistical significance. Furthermore, there is no discernible impact of the constant term on the co-integrating relationship.

R-squared is a statistical significance measure that expresses a percentage of the variance of the dependent variable that can be explained by the independent variables in the regression model. R-squared is 0.824, meaning that 82.41% of the variance in the dependent variable is explained by the independent variables in the model. The Adjusted R-squared of 0.724 means that approximately 72.42% of the variability in the dependent variable is explained by the independent variables in the regression model, taking into account the number of predictors. The idea of log-likelihood is used to quantify how well a statistical model can predict observed data.

The log-likelihood value of 84.746 for the model suggests that it fits the observed data quite accurately. The sum of squared residuals (0.364) indicates that real data points and the model's predictions are nearly identical. The results of the Schwarz Criterion (-0.843) and AIC (-1.679) point to a well-fitting, simple, and balanced model. The decreased standard error of 0.091 shows that the model can predict values with appropriate precision that are within a range of the actual values. The regression model's overall significance is supported by the high F-statistic (8.247). Collectively, these graphs show how well the model corresponds to the data while maintaining a reasonable level of complexity.

5. Conclusion and Discussion

In conclusion, this study aims to provide more insight into the historical patterns of GDP growth, gross national happiness (GNH) health expenditures, and education expenditures in Pakistan. The study not only indicates that health and education relate to subjective well-being and wealth, but it also focuses on the variables that influence these aspects. Real GDP per capita (RGDP), health expenditures (HEX), and education expenditures (EEX) are significant long-term economic indicators of happiness (HAP), according to the study's co-integration analysis.

There is a positive association between happiness and RGDP (-0.096219), indicating that a higher GDP per capita boosts happiness levels and is consistent with the notion that a greater amount of money improves living standards and overall well-being. This stands in opposition to the Easterlin Paradox, which maintains that wealth has declining returns to well-being beyond a certain threshold. Additionally, there is a positive correlation (0.835942) between happiness and education spending, indicating that increasing educational spending improves well-being.

The relationship between happiness and education expenditures is also positive (-0.835942), suggesting that investing more in education enhances well-being. Human capital theory argues that education improves people's skills and productivity, which benefits them in terms of employment opportunities, income, and quality of life—all of which are necessary for a happy life.

Conversely, there is a negative relationship (-0.678971) between higher health expenditure and happiness. This surprising result could be the result of several factors. Inefficiencies in the healthcare system, such as resource misallocation, corruption, or administrative problems that result in substantial expenses without corresponding improvements in health outcomes may infuriate the public. Moreover, changes in medical

practices or rising costs may short-term anxiety and concern, which could undermine people's sense of their well-being. As well, rather than attempting to prevent problems, spending on healthcare may be more reactive, concentrating on solving them as they come up. Financial stress is a major factor in health difficulties and associated medical costs, which reduces happiness.

This study suggests that if Pakistan wants to achieve long-term economic growth and general well-being, it has to give health and education priority. The way these components interact and the necessity of coordinated growth strategies are brought to light by a thorough analysis of quarterly data from 2003 to 2022. As a means of promoting sustainable development and societal well-being, the findings underscore the need to put health and education policies into practice. The research provides insightful perspectives that encourage policymakers and other relevant stakeholders to recognize the relationships and act toward a more equitable and prosperous future for everyone. It is advised to improve healthcare systems, increase the effectiveness of education spending, and strike a balance between economic growth and well-being.

Creating inclusive health and education initiatives, keeping an eye on and assessing laws, and encouraging inclusive development are a few instances of useful approaches. The implementation of these particular activities and suggestions will improve the study's overall impact and practical ramifications, as well as fortify and substantiate the arguments.

6. References

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